

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

CYBERSECURITY IN THE AUTOMOTIVE INDUSTRY: VULNERABILITIES AND PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

Protection against cyber threats in the automotive industry is one of the most crucial aspects of ensuring the safety of vehicles equipped with information and communication systems. The article analyzes existing vulnerabilities and their consequences for car users, manufacturers, and society. It examines various types of threats and attacks, as well as modern protection methods. The necessity for joint efforts by automotive market participants to ensure cybersecurity in vehicle internal systems is emphasized.

Keywords: cybersecurity, automotive systems, cyber threats, protection methods, safety standards.

Introduction

Cybersecurity in the automotive industry has become one of the most crucial aspects with the development of vehicles equipped with complex information and communication structures. Modern cars contain onboard computers, driver assistance systems, telematics, and infotainment systems, which provide a high level of comfort and safety for drivers and passengers. But these technologies make vehicles vulnerable to various cyber threats. According to the 2024 report [1], the number of incidents related to cyber-attacks on automotive vehicles has increased by more than 50% between 2019 and 2023, reaching 295 reported incidents in 2023. Of these, 95% of attacks occurred remotely, while 64% were perpetrated by black hat actors in 2023.

Automotive manufacturers are now implementing measures to guarantee that their vehicles comply with cybersecurity standards and are more resilient to potential cyber threats. It is becoming increasingly common for automotive companies to set up specialised teams

dedicated to cybersecurity, tasked with researching potential security risks and developing strategies to address them. In order to safeguard their vehicles against threats, manufacturers can invest in measures that protect against them, thus ensuring their vehicles' long-term security and simultaneously promoting innovation in vehicle technology and automotive systems (AS).

The objective of this paper is to examine the various types of threats, attacks, and their consequences, as well as the modern methods and technologies employed for the protection of automotive systems.

Main part. Vulnerabilities in automotive systems

The ongoing evolution of connectivity is transforming the automotive and smart mobility ecosystem, simultaneously increasing cybersecurity risks and expanding the scope for potential vulnerabilities. The year 2023 marked the advent of a new era in automotive cybersecurity, characterized by a persistent and pervasive problem of personally identifiable information leakage (PII), vulnerability exploits, and other related issues (fig. 1).

Figure 1. Black hat and fraud operators' activities areas of interest, 2023 [1]

A considerable number of AS and components have been constructed upon technologies that were not initially designed with cybersecurity measures taken into consideration. The implementation of these actions onto AS presents a considerable challenge for the automotive cybersecurity teams tasked with this endeavor.

The use of open-source software and the involvement of multiple suppliers in the development process further complicates the already challenging task of securing the automotive supply chain.

The global automotive industry experienced a multitude of cyber-related challenges between 2010 and 2023 (fig. 2).

Figure 2. Cybercrime impact in automotive companies worldwide from 2010 to 2023, by type [2]

A vulnerability in one area can potentially spread to other parts of the enterprise, leading to adverse consequences such as vehicle malfunction, production delays, the compromise of customer data, or the theft of intellectual property. In order to ensure the safety of cars, it is necessary to implement an enterprise-wide programme that coordinates cyber defenses across all production platforms, internal operations, and supply chains.

Vulnerabilities in software and electronics

Modern vehicles are equipped with numerous electronic control units (ECUs) that manage various functions of the car, from the engine to driver assistance systems. The software controlling these units may contain vulnerabilities that allow unauthorized access to the vehicle's systems. Many ECUs can be hacked through diagnostic ports such as OBD-II (On-Board Diagnostics), enabling attackers to alter the car's settings or even take control of its operation.

Wireless communication threats. Wireless technologies (Bluetooth, Wi-Fi, and 4G/5G mobile networks) provide additional entry points for cyberattacks. Vehicles connected to the internet and using wireless communication can be vulnerable to MITM (Man-in-the-Middle) attacks, where an attacker intercepts and alters transmitted data. Vulnerabilities in Bluetooth can allow an attacker to connect to the vehicle's system and gain access to confidential data or vehicle functions [3].

Risks associated with connecting vehicles to the internet. One of the primary concerns is the susceptibility to remote cyber-attacks, where malicious actors can exploit software weaknesses to gain unauthorized access to the vehicle's control systems. Such breaches can lead to manipulation of critical functions, including braking, steering, and acceleration, potentially causing accidents or enabling theft. Internet-connected vehicles are prone to data breaches, where sensitive information such as location data, personal details, and driving habits can be intercepted and misused. The integration of vehicles into the broader internet ecosystem also exposes them to malware and ransomware attacks, which can disrupt operations and necessitate costly repairs. Implementing robust cybersecurity measures, continuous monitoring, and fostering collaborative efforts

among manufacturers, regulators, and cybersecurity experts are essential to mitigate these risks and protect both functionality and user privacy.

Vulnerabilities in navigation systems and driver assistance systems. Advanced Driver Assistance Systems are also susceptible to cyberattacks. Vulnerabilities in navigation technologies can allow attackers to alter routes and disorient the driver by sending fake GPS signals to the system. Driver assistance systems, such as adaptive cruise control and automatic emergency braking, can be hacked and modified, potentially leading to accidents [4].

Types of attacks on automotive systems and their consequences

As vehicles become increasingly networked, their systems become more vulnerable to cyberattacks. Such attacks may range in severity from minor glitches to serious security breaches that compromise the privacy of passengers and drivers.

DoS (Denial-of-Service) and DDoS (Distributed Denial-of-Service) attacks aim to overload the system, rendering it inaccessible to the user. These attacks can incapacitate a vehicle or disrupt the operation of critical functions. **MITM (Man-in-the-Middle)** attacks involve intercepting and altering data transmitted between vehicle systems. Such actions include manipulating control commands or location data. **Phishing attacks** involve sending fake emails to vehicle owners, aiming to gain access to their accounts for unauthorized access. **SQL injection** attacks target databases containing information about vehicles and their owners. Attackers can alter vehicle maintenance parameters, leading to inaccurate information about the vehicle's condition [5].

Cyberattacks on AS can have serious consequences for drivers and passengers. If control over key vehicle functions is seized by attackers, there is an immediate **threat to road safety**. Such situations may cause accidents, posing a risk to the lives of the driver, passengers, and other road users.

An attack on a vehicle's internal systems can result in **economic losses** for manufacturers. Following cyberattacks, companies may face the need to recall vehicles, deal with lawsuits, and suffer a loss of customer

trust. In some cases, the costs of system recovery, compensation to vehicle owners, and reputational damage can be significant.

Cyberattacks have **social consequences**. By hacking vehicle systems, attackers can gain access to information about location, routes, and even personal data of vehicle owners, opening up opportunities for blackmail or other illegal activities. Intrusion into AS negatively impact trust in modern technologies and slow down the adoption of innovations and the development of the transportation industry.

In 2022, a team of security experts and researchers discovered numerous vulnerabilities in vehicles from 16 different automotive companies [6]. It allowed them to access a carmaker's internal applications and systems, resulting in the exposure of customer and employee PII and account takeover. The hacks targeted telematics systems, automotive APIs (Application Programming Interface) and infrastructure.

The researchers were able to remotely control a variety of functions on the vehicle, including starting and stopping the engine, locking and unlocking the vehicle, flashing the headlights, sounding the horn, and retrieving the precise location of Acura, Honda, Kia, Infiniti, and Nissan cars, using only the VIN (vehicle identification number). They could restrict users' access to remote vehicle management and could alter the status of vehicle ownership. In the case of Kia's, it was possible to access the 360-degree camera view and observe the real-time images captured by the vehicle.

Another group of American cyber security researchers employed the most recent hacking techniques to gain unauthorized access to the electrical systems of a Jeep Cherokee [7]. The researchers succeeded in attaining wireless control of the automobile, thereby enabling them to relay commands to its dashboard functions, steering, brakes, and transmission. They achieved this feat from a distance of 10 miles from the vehicle's original location.

These examples underscore that cyberattacks on AS pose a threat to both safety and economic stability, as well as to public trust. Automotive manufacturers and software developers must pay special attention to cybersecurity, develop and implement modern protection methods, and continuously update systems to guard against new threats [8].

Protection methods and countermeasures

Modern methods for protecting AS include the use of advanced technologies such as intrusion detection and prevention systems (IDS/IPS), artificial intelligence, and machine learning. These technologies analyze network traffic and device behavior to detect anomalies and potential threats. An important element of protection is the implementation of update mechanisms and patch management, which allow timely remediation of software vulnerabilities. Collaborative efforts among manufacturers, suppliers, and regulators also play a key role in protecting AS. The creation and implementation of safety standards, conducting joint research, and sharing information about cyber threats help reduce risks in vehicle use.

Developing secure software for the automotive industry involves several stages: analyzing security requirements and identifying potential threats, designing system architecture considering identified risks and vulnerabilities, programming and testing, deploying software, and monitoring it. It is crucial to constantly monitor the system's status, identify, and address new vulnerabilities. Another essential aspect of cybersecurity is the implementation of effective update and patch management mechanisms. These features facilitate the prompt remediation of software vulnerabilities, which includes the modernization and upgrading of system components.

Encryption and authentication are critical elements in protecting AS. Encryption secures data against unauthorized access and tampering, while authentication verifies the authenticity of users and devices. An example of the successful use of encryption and authentication is the blockchain system, which provides a high degree of reliability and transparency. In the automotive industry, it can be used to protect data on vehicle manufacturing, maintenance, and operation [9].

Standards and regulations establish a minimum level of protection and encourage manufacturers to adopt the most effective safety practices. An example of such a standard is **ISO/SAE 21434**, which was released by the International Organization for Standardization (ISO) and the Society of Automotive Engineers (SAE) at the end of August 2021 [10]. The main elements of this standard include security management, cybersecurity management for specific projects, and continuous cybersecurity activities. The document establishes appropriate risk and cybersecurity assessment methodologies in the context of conceptual product development and post-development stages of road vehicles.

NHTSA (National Highway Traffic Safety Administration, part of the U.S. Department of Transportation) has released **voluntary guidelines** with the intention of assisting automotive manufacturers in addressing cybersecurity risks [11]. The guides were developed as resources for the industry on a range of important vehicle cybersecurity issues, including incident response, collaboration and engagement with appropriate third parties, governance, risk assessment and management, awareness and training.

Conclusion

Ensuring cybersecurity in the automotive industry is crucial for users of vehicles equipped with complex information and communication structures. These technologies enhance the comfort of travel but also make vehicles vulnerable to various cyber threats. Therefore, automotive system cybersecurity requires continuous monitoring, improvement of protection methods, adoption of advanced technologies, and compliance with safety standards. An integrated approach and close cooperation among automotive industry participants will effectively counter cyber threats and ensure the safety of drivers and passengers.

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